

SPECIAL ISSUE ARTICLE**Blockchain-based SLA Management for 6G Networks**Farhana Javed*¹ | Josep Mangles-Bafalluy²

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In this letter, we propose the use of a blockchain-based solution for inter-provider agreements in 6G networks, utilizing smart contracts and Chainlink for monitoring and assessing Service Level Agreements (SLAs), including penalty calculations. We evaluate the proposed solution by deploying it on two public blockchains, Ethereum and Polygon, and find that Polygon provides a cost-effective option for creating inter-provider agreements. This is particularly important for use cases involving numerous transactions. Additionally, Chainlink enables secure and transparent access to off-chain SLA data, and we observe lower transaction latency in Polygon. This suggests that utilizing blockchain-based solutions such as smart contracts can aid the process of creating inter-provider agreements for leasing and selling resources in 6G networks, with Chainlink oracle providing support for their SLA management. However, factors such as transaction cost and latency need to be considered.

KEYWORDS:

Blockchain, 6G, Chainlink, Inter-Provider, Smart contract

1 | INTRODUCTION

According to the *European Vision for the 6G Ecosystem*¹, a 6G network is anticipated to facilitate dynamic multi-domain network slicing with numerous inter-provider agreements. As a result, 6G networks are projected to significantly expand the number of stakeholders involved in service offerings due to softwarization. In this context, deploying multi-domain network services necessitates advanced solutions, such as *service federation*. *Federation* refers to the orchestration of services or resources across multiple domains. The concept of service federation has been explored in the 5Growth project².

An *inter-provider agreement* is essential for orchestrating network slices across several administrative domains, ensuring secure and transparent processes³. Service providers are exploring new models, such as platforms or NFV marketplaces, to sell, lease, or procure resources and services with defined Service Level Agreements (SLAs). These SLAs facilitate automated onboarding of assets, resource sharing, and ensure accountability and transparency. Typically, SLAs define Service Level Objectives (SLOs) based on Quality of Service (QoS) metrics and financial penalties for any SLO violations. In 6G networks, transparent, cost-effective, and monitorable inter-provider agreements are paramount. These can be realized through SLA monitoring using blockchain technology⁴.

In our previous research³, we explored how decentralized blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) might bolster inter-provider agreements using smart contracts. These contracts can facilitate the leasing or selling of resources and monitor SLAs. Furthermore, these agreements can either be static, where terms are fixed, or dynamic to cater to on-demand service creation. For instance, consumer domains could initiate a reverse auction (where providers bid to offer services at the most competitive rates) on a blockchain-based Decentralized Application (DApp). Other provider domains can then submit bids, with smart contracts determining the winner based on criteria set by the consumer domain⁵.

This letter builds on our earlier findings presented in⁶, emphasizing the advantages of smart contracts for ensuring distributed trust and immutable records. It also underscores the importance of off-chain access to external data logs for monitoring SLAs and computing Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), with the assumption of data accuracy and reliability. The concept of Chainlink

was introduced earlier: a decentralized network connecting smart contracts to external data sources and APIs, ensuring accurate information and incentivizing nodes using *LINK* tokens. LINK is Chainlink’s native token that rewards node operators and facilitates data transfers between contracts and external sources.

We introduce a framework that employs Chainlink to automate compensation processes for SLA breaches. This is achieved by linking off-chain data logs with on-chain penalty calculations, leveraging Chainlink’s automation to obtain data at various intervals. This enables smart contracts to monitor both SLAs and KPIs. Furthermore, our system suggests using this data to compute penalties and manage the billing process. This is evaluated using the Ethereum and Polygon blockchains concerning cost and performance.

The structure of this letter is as follows: Section 2 provides a background on blockchain, inter-provider agreements, and related works. Section 3 presents our primary contribution: a blockchain-based SLA monitoring system for 6G networks focusing on inter-provider agreements. Evaluation is detailed in Section 4, and concluding remarks are found in Section 5.

2 | BACKGROUND: INTER-PROVIDER AGREEMENTS IN 6G NETWORKS

To support 6G network use cases, the concept of *inter-provider agreements* allows Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) and service providers to share resources to cater to the needs of diverse verticals. However, these agreements need to have transparency and trust. SLA monitoring is crucial to establishing trust in a transparent yet secure way. That is where the concept of blockchain comes into play. Blockchain technology is designed to be highly resistant to tampering which can potentially enhance the integrity and reliability of SLA monitoring. Smart contracts and DApps on blockchain technology can be used to establish agreements between providers, with blockchain-based oracles such as Chainlink monitoring SLAs, and smart contracts enforcing the SLA by automatically releasing payments or penalties based on compliance data logs recorded on the blockchain. Previously, a blockchain-based slice broker has been proposed in⁷ and⁸ where the authors proposed an approach for resource allocation using blockchain and smart contracts. Similarly, in⁹, the authors present a blockchain and smart contract-based E2E architecture for network sharing. Moreover, the authors propose a concept where a customer (tenant) can request a mobile network operator for network services. However, the method of SLA monitoring is omitted, and the issue of SLA monitoring in network sharing still needs to be addressed. The authors in¹⁰ provide a blockchain-based architecture for network slice auctions. In this work, infrastructure providers allocate network slices through an intermediary entity that provides resources to tenants. However, the idea needs to address the issue of SLA monitoring.

This letter emphasizes the significance of SLA monitoring in 6G networks for ensuring QoS. It proposes leveraging off-chain data sources to monitor KPIs, an aspect that has received limited attention in existing literature. While smart contracts can automate terms and conditions, accessing off-chain data sources plays a critical role in effective SLA monitoring. The letter highlights the potential of decentralized oracles like Chainlink to bridge the gap between off-chain data and smart contracts. Notably, the use of Chainlink for data monitoring in the context of SLA has not been previously addressed. Thus, the letter introduces the application of Chainlink to monitor SLA data logs obtained from off-chain sources at regular intervals. The proposed framework combines Chainlink’s monitoring capabilities with smart contracts to address disputes, enforce penalties for pre-defined SLA breaches, and streamline the billing process based on SLA logs.

3 | PROPOSED WORK

The 5Growth (5Gr) architecture enables service federation between different entities¹¹, which has three main building blocks in its Management and Orchestration (MANO) stack including the Vertical Slicer (5Gr-VS), the SO (5Gr-SO), the Resource Layer (5Gr-RL). This Section proposes a blockchain-enabled architecture in Figure 1 that combines 5Growth modules, and the Vertical-oriented monitoring system (VoMS) to collect, store, and process operational data based on metrics received from deployed services.

Workflow of the proposed methodology

The general flow of blockchain-enabled SLA monitoring is shown in Figure. 1: We divide the interaction of the platform with the blockchain into three phases: Phase 1 steps (steps 1 to 3) in the Figure are shown in color red, whereas Phase 2 steps (step 4) in the Figure are shown in color blue. Lastly Phase 3 is shown in color green (step 5 and 6). In Figure 1, **P** represents the steps performed by provider domain and **C**, shows the steps performed by consumer domain.

Registration and service selection: Phase 1: Administrative domains (ADs) can interact with the DApp and register themselves on the blockchain through the DApp to either publish their offers on the DApp or to browse the available services on the Marketplace (**step P-1 & C-1**). ADs create a catalog of services, which consists of an eligibility list of agreed and offered Network Function Virtualization-Network Services (NFV-NSs), that is stored via InterPlanetary File System (IPFS) (**step P-2**)

Figure 1 Functional Blockchain/DLT-based SLA management for inter-provider agreement: Key components and their interaction

and published as a hash on the DApp for consumer ADs to view if interested. The *Marketplace.sol* smart contract facilitates these interactions, such as registering, listing services, or selecting a service. Consumer ADs can search and select available services on the DApps (**step C-2**), and upon selection, a request is sent to the provider AD for service deployment.

Additionally, consumer ADs can request an auction (**step C-3**) for dynamic solutions to customized services, with a new smart contract *Auction.sol* created for each request, and bids submitted by provider ADs via the smart contract on the blockchain (**step P-3**). A winner is selected based on the auction mechanism and internal policy criteria, with the selected winning provider AD executing the request.

SLA logs monitoring: Phase 2: Our proposed approach for SLA management assumes the accuracy and reliability of the monitoring data, which is ingested into smart contracts via Chainlink. Once the data is added to the smart contract, it becomes tamper-proof, as it is recorded on the blockchain and cannot be altered. We leverage Chainlink for providing selected KPIs or filtered logs to consumer ADs, while the 5Gr-API subscribes to internal log messages relevant to the message queue component or 5Gr-VoMS. An automation job runs on Chainlink to ingest real-time monitoring data from the 5Gr-API, enabling seamless integration with the proposed SLA management framework. Moreover, the creation of the *SLA.sol* smart contract is triggered when the services start to run (**step P-4**). In our use case, consumer ADs send specific requests for filter data for real-time monitoring of SLAs (**step C-4**), and can request periodic data feeds based on their use case requirements. The logs are stored in the *SLA.sol*, and each time smart contract is triggered when Chainlink processes the requests, with data logs fetched from the API by Chainlink's smart contract *Oracle.sol*.

Penalties and billing: Phase 3: To ensure appropriate configuration, management, and maintenance of services, monitoring functions must be accessible to all stakeholders. Penalties may be assigned based on the breach B . This letter considers the service uptime T_{up} as one metric for the breach occurrence to impose a penalties. To calculate the total T_{up} , we use $T_{up} = \frac{T_{total} - T_{delay}}{T_{total}}$; where the total time T_{total} of a service dedicated to a particular service and the total unavailable time as delay T_{delay} of that specific service. In this proposed idea we are considering if the breach B happens, it should be solved as soon as possible. After solving the breach B , a penalty P is calculated according to the source and degree of the breach (**step P-5 & C-5**), which will be deducted from the amount agreed to provider AD. In case of a breach B , our scheme assumes that the service provider and consumer AD agree on an individual threshold of each monitoring metric for a penalty. Moreover, we divided T_{up} of service into three ranges: required T_{up} (e.g. = 100%), average T_{up} (e.g. $\geq 95.5\%$), and low T_{up} (e.g. $\leq 90\%$) in order to help both the provider and the consumer AD to evaluate whether the measured metrics of a service meet, exceed, or fall below the predefined levels in a certain period. The breach is calculated using the formula above after every t , which can be set to 1, 2 or 3 minutes. Following the completion of service deployment, the smart contract created for the service remains active until payment is transferred from the consumer's wallet to the provider's wallet. The provider AD may request funds (**step P-6**), and the payment will be transferred from the consumer AD to the provider AD if the consumer is satisfied (**step C-6**).

4 | DEPLOYMENT AND EVALUATION

This Section presents an evaluation of the proposed framework, which involves two parties: the consumer and provider AD. Both are registered independently via a smart contract on two public blockchain testnets, Ethereum and Polygon. The evaluation aims to assess the feasibility and performance of the approach on public blockchains, deploying the smart contracts on the Goerli (Ethereum) and Mumbai (Polygon) testnets with an Ubuntu 14.04 operating system, 2 GB RAM, and 8 GB disk memory. Goerli and Mumbai are test networks for Ethereum and Polygon blockchains, respectively. They are designed to provide a testing environment for developers to test their DApps and smart contracts before deploying them to the main network. By testing the proposed work on multiple testnets such as Goerli and Mumbai, this study aims to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of how the proposed work functions in different environments. This provides a thorough assessment of its performance, accounting for variations in network conditions. Comparative analysis further enables this study to identify factors that may influence the performance of the proposed work, such as network architecture or consensus mechanism. Furthermore, the aim of this study is to evaluate blockchain networks like Ethereum and Polygon so as to enable stakeholders to identify the most suitable network for their use case based on performance metrics such as transaction speed, block time, and gas fees. This can inform decision-making around network selection and cost-effectiveness, particularly for high-volume transactions. To monitor the performance, 5000 transactions were executed on both the Goerli and Mumbai testnets.

4.1 | Overall cost estimation

To assess the efficacy of the proposed work concerning transaction fees and overall cost, the following transaction fees and costs have been considered to provide the analyses of the overall cost: (1) The transaction fees incurred during the execution of smart contracts in both the Ethereum testnet (Goerli) and the Polygon testnet (Mumbai) across all three phases described earlier in Section 3. (2): LINK amount paid for off chain data access during the Phase 2. Figure 2 illustrates the transaction fees for all smart contracts deployed on the Ethereum and Polygon testnets. Transaction fees, also known as gas fees, are the charges levied for executing transactions on public blockchains. The fees are utilized to reward the network nodes for the computational resources required to process and verify the transaction. In Ethereum, the transaction fee (in ETH) is computed by multiplying the gas limit (maximum gas allowed for the transaction) by the gas price (ETH paid per unit of gas). In contrast, on the Polygon network, the transaction fee (in MATIC) is determined by multiplying the gas limit by the gas price, where the gas price is expressed in Gwei (1 Gwei = 0.000000001 MATIC), the smallest unit of currency on the Polygon network. Given the diverse functionalities and use cases of ETH and MATIC, comparing them poses challenges. To assess smart contract deployment fees on both public blockchains uniformly, we use USD as a standardized unit of measurement (as of April 2023, accounting for fluctuating conversions).

The transaction fee is calculated for each smart contract deployed in Ethereum and Polygon testnets. Figure 2a and Figure 2c display the cost of the proposed work in ETH and MATIC, while Figure 2b and Figure 2d show the corresponding USD conversions from ETH and MATIC, respectively. It is observed that smart contracts deployed on Ethereum testnet are higher than Polygon. Transaction fees are generally higher in Ethereum than in Polygon due to differences in the two networks' underlying technology and fee models. The observed differences in transaction fees between the Goerli and Mumbai testnets could be attributed to various factors. One potential factor is the variance in network congestion levels, as the Goerli testnet is a prominent platform for Ethereum developers and may encounter higher levels of activity compared to the Mumbai testnet. Another factor is the variation in gas prices and gas limit settings implemented during transactions. Lastly, the transaction fee is higher in different smart contracts as it can be observed in the Figure 2. The higher transaction fees in Oracle.sol and SLA.sol are due to the complexity of the transactions required to execute their functions, specifically the off-chain data access and penalty calculation handled in Phases 2 and 3. As a result, smart contracts with more complex transactions requiring more computational resources tend to have higher fees than simpler contracts, such as Marketplace.sol, Auction.sol, and Billing.sol.

In addition to transaction fee of smart contracts, Chainlink incentivizes node operators to provide accurate and reliable off-chain data access by using its cryptocurrency, LINK, as payment. The Chainlink automation is also used and set to a time interval of $t = 1, 2, \text{ or } 3$ minutes. Figure 3, shows the amount of LINK paid during different intervals for off-chain data access. The amount of LINK required for off-chain data access in Chainlink is determined by several factors, including the complexity of the data request, the reputation of the node operator providing the data, and the market price of LINK at the time of the request. Figure 3a and 3b demonstrate the variation in LINK payment when deploying the Oracle.sol smart contract on Ethereum's Goerli testnet and Polygon testnet, respectively. The Chainlink off-chain data access cost may be higher when utilizing Goerli testnet due to factors such as network congestion and node operator availability. Conversely, the cost of Chainlink is generally lower when utilizing Polygon testnet, as it is designed for faster and cheaper transactions and optimized for deploying and running smart contracts, requiring fewer computational resources to process off-chain data requests.

Figure 2 Transaction fee estimation for Ethereum and Polygon testnet

Figure 3 Off-chain data access in Phase 2: Amount paid in LINK using Chainlink for *Oracle.sol* with Ethereum and Polygon testnet

4.2 | Overall latency estimation

Transaction latency in blockchain networks is the time taken for a transaction to be validated and added to the blockchain, and that it can be affected by various factors such as block size, network congestion, transaction fees, consensus mechanism, and the number of nodes. However, to gain a fundamental understanding of the observed latency we are calculating the latency for three phases (i.e., registration, monitoring and billing) using the following expression: $Latency = T_{confirmation} - T_{submission}$. The transaction confirmation time is the time at which the transaction is confirmed and added to the blockchain, while the transaction submission time is the time at which the transaction is submitted to the network. The difference between the two times gives the latency of the transaction.

Figure 4 shows the latency observed in three phases (creation, monitoring and billing), as explained in above Section 3. The monitoring phase of inter-provider agreements in 6G networks has been observed to suffer from higher latency than the creation and billing phases, due to several factors. These factors include the time taken for the data source to respond to the request, the time taken for the data to be transmitted across the network and received by the requesting smart contract, the number of nodes involved in the process, and network congestion and high gas fees. Chainlink's off-chain data access can experience additional latency as it fetches data from off-chain sources and these transactions are confirmed on the blockchain. In conclusion, the results suggest that the Polygon network offers lower cost and latency compared to Ethereum's Goerli testnet. This can be attributed to Polygon's use of *sidechains* (*sidechains* in Polygon are independent, parallel chains that can run their own consensus mechanisms and manage their own transactions, while still being connected to the main Polygon network.) to reduce computational load, enabling a higher transaction volume at a lower cost. The difference in network congestion and node availability could be the reason why Chainlink data access is faster on the Mumbai testnet than on the Goerli testnet.

5 | CONCLUSION

This letter presents a use case for blockchain technology in the context of 6G networks, specifically emphasizing inter-provider agreements and the role of blockchain. The proposed solution is structured around three key phases: creating agreements using smart contracts, monitoring SLAs, and enforcing penalties and billing. The SLAs are monitored using a blockchain oracle, notably Chainlink, in conjunction with smart contracts, which ensures secure and transparent SLA data access for enforcing penalties and facilitating billing for SLA assessment. Both Ethereum and Polygon are employed to evaluate the performance of the proposed solution. However, the incorporation of Chainlink does lead to additional costs. Specifically, the results suggest that Ethereum incurs a substantially higher expense in comparison to Polygon. Additionally, Ethereum experiences a comparatively

Figure 4 Latency for three phases (Phase 1: Registration and service selection, Phase 2: SLA logs and monitoring, Phase 3: Penalties and billing) in Ethereum and Polygon higher average latency, which can peak at around ≈ 25 seconds during the monitoring phase. On the other hand, Polygon’s architecture, which leverages "sidechains", contributes to both reduced costs and latency. For our forthcoming endeavors, we aim to implement measures that enhance the reliability of monitoring data sourced from mobile operators. These measures will encompass the deployment of regulatory methods to ensure the data delivered by these operators remains both accurate and trustworthy.

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